

BISTATIC LAPTOP RADAR *
An Affordable, Silent Radar Alternative

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ABSTRACT

Passive sensor technology based on noncooperative, coherent broadband sensing can provide a lower power consumption, low cost, light weight and compact (man portable) alternative to active radar sensors in support of quiet surveillance and radio frequency (RF) target imaging. The AF Rome Laboratory and its sponsored industrial community (Syracuse Research Corp, Decision Science Applications, Inc, Technology Service Corp, etc.) have been developing and testing such a passive sensor technology since the early '80's. This development has been based on an integrated electromagnetic support measures (ESM) and broadband coherent passive sensing technology. The goal of this development is to provide a highly efficient, very low power demanding, affordable alternative to active radar, as well as gaining immediately the associable advantages of this technology, which, by its very construction and operating configuration, lends itself to being minimally burnable in weight, size, power consumption, thusly supporting man-portability. This presents significant advantages for applications such as counter narcotics drug interdiction, covert surveillance, etc.

INTRODUCTION

System applications of this technology benefit from its inherent features of being able to conduct target sensing in a multi-frequency manner thus optimizing the acquisition of target observables phenomenology which lends to target characterization and classification, leading to the potentials of target identification (ID). A further advantages of this sensor technology, which independently exploits background signals as surveillance hostile illuminators in a noncooperative illuminator manner, is its ease in augmenting existing active sensors for enhancements in their surveillance coverage, as well as assuring hosted sensor/platform survivability do to its quiet operation. These later features provide significant merits in applications such as covert surveillance, smuggling interdiction, and, enhancing existing system surveillance coverage without demanding system compatibility or synchronization/network burdens.

With references to Fig 1A and Fig 1B, the principles of this technology lie in the ability to randomly and coherently intercept broadband signals within large regions of the radio frequency (RF) spectrum, and to coherently (coherent-on-receiver) exploit these signals for the purposes of passive surveillance operating modes. The technical research conducted over several years at Rome Laboratory (RL) has perfected the integration of Electromagnetic Support Measures (ESM) techniques (which fundamentally are radiometric surveillance modes) with coherent noncooperative passive sensing, establishing a powerful integrated ESM/passive sensor technology which lends itself to multiple-mode quiet surveillance operations as well as multiple frequency detection / tracking and target signal phenomenology interception capabilities. Further, if the noncooperative waveform has sufficient bandwidth, the waveform exploitation process can implement RF target imaging based on passive synthetic aperture radar (P-SAR) principles to within the surveillance processing capacity of the exploited waveform, or the

* Presented at the IEEE 1996 National Radar Conference, Ann Arbor, Michigan, 13-16 May 1996.

surveillance/monitoring conditions. Even if the exploited waveform is not wide band, RF imaging can still be achieved by coherent inverse synthetic aperture radar (ISAR) approaches which are inherently supported by the coherent nature of the RL passive surveillance and imaging technology. One of its key technological features which supports these coherent processes is its noncooperative, coherent pulse chasing which is first implemented by the ESM waveform discovery/analysis process, and, secondly established by the coherent noncooperative operations themselves. The research being conducted at RL has addressed perfecting this integrated ESM / passive surveillance technology for both static (fixed ground targets) and dynamic (airborne and moving ground targets) applications. Currently, an airborne ESM/passive sensor testbed has been built and is used for varied applications testing. Recent studies have addressed the problems of passively exploiting ground based velocity ambiguous waveforms from the airborne ESM/passive sensor testbed for quiet, long range air and ground target surveillance modes. These tests have been successful, implementing modifications to this hybrid technology so that the ambiguous problems which arise in this application can be solved. These airborne tests and demonstrations will continue under a research program known as Adaptive Mode Surveillance (AMBIS).

Figure 1. Sensor Concept

Rome Laboratory (RL) bistatic technology is based on noncooperative coherent exploitation of random background ambient signals. Signal exploitation is for purposes of airborne and ground based target detection, tracking and target typing / ID. The noncooperative exploited signal can be narrow band or wide band, any carrier frequency from HF (tens of MHz) through X-band (tens of Ghz), and supporting any processing mode, from COMM, through broadcast services, or radar surveillance or imaging. The historical beginning of the RL bistatic technology addressed the detection of small signal low altitude targets in an augmentation capacity supporting other primary systems which could not detect such target threats. The more recent research has focused on extending the successful small signal target detection and tracking performance by adding target typing capabilities, leading to target imaging as a hybrid detection/tracking mode of operation. The RL coherent noncooperative bistatics technology has an inherent target typing/imaging capability in that it combines an electronic support measures (ESM) capability with passive surveillance functions (target range, velocity, and angular location information as PSI track file displays in real time). Target typing is accomplished by combining target measured radar cross-section (RCS), target flight kinematics, target equipment signal emissions (ESM mode), and emitted signal finger printing (unintentional modulation on pulse-UMOP) via the integrated ESM/passive sensing nature of the RL technology. The current work is extending this technology to conduct integrated surveillance and target typing/imaging while remaining a passive sensor technology.

These developments and test results establish the credibility of considering this RL technology as an affordable, low cost, light weight alternative to active radar sensors. The technical area of focus addressing the

remote capabilities of this portable technology led to the porting of all software and signal processing algorithms associated with this technology onto a laptop personal computer. The same critical performance testing conducted with the vehicle based testbeds were than revisited using the laptop sensor configuration. Greater portability and mission operability was proven possible with this laptop sensor configuration.

The operational concept of broadband passive sensor technology is shown in Fig. 1A as a multi-mode operating sensor system. The corresponding sensor processing flow is shown in Fig. 1B as having three parallel output products. The first of its primary principles (or operating modes) is the awareness of noncooperative, ambient background signals, serving as ambient illuminators. This awareness is afforded by a passive signal intercept and waveform parameter analysis mode, which is the electronic support measures (ESM) mode. This mode provides ambient illuminator monitoring, cataloging and selection for passive surveillance exploitation. It is represented in Fig. 1A and Fig. 1B as the passive receiver sampling an ambient illuminator via a direct path reference beam. The ambient illuminator selection for the passive surveillance mode is based on factors governed by waveform ambiguity properties versus desired passive radar operations, illuminator signal strength (illumination power level), and, general surveillance mode operation factors which include the effective surveillance geometry (a particular illuminator-target-passive receiver arrangement synthesizes a particular surveillance geometry).

Figure 1B. Sensor Signal Processing Flow

The second of the primary principles (second operating mode of this multi-mode passive sensor, see Fig. 1B) is the passive detection of the target echo. Under this mode, the receiver coherently processes this echo with the direct path sample of the ambient illuminator. The broadband, multi-frequency noncooperative coherent operation of the passive surveillance receiver supports the selection of many illuminators (however only one is actually needed), and consequently, many target echoes. Only those echoes which are coherent with the direct path sample will provide a useful result in the coherent-noncooperative process employed by the passive surveillance receiver. Via the ESM mode, the illuminator selection is controlled from the signals awareness processing in order to coherently exploit the direct path for target echo processing. This processing produces real-time measurements of target range, range rate (and higher order target kinematics), and, angular bearing of the target echo arrival. These measurements are exactly what active radar measures when monitoring the land, sea, or air activity. Thus, they directly support real-time, multiple target tracking and positional display, as shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2. Passive Sensor Target Tracking Display

AN APPLICATION EXAMPLE

Going from the first principles concept of operations, as shown in Figs 1A and 1B, to an actually fabricated passive, multi-mode sensor, will reveal how this sensor concept is reduced to practice. An airborne variant of the passive sensor was fabricated and flown as an airborne passive sensor testbed. The airborne passive sensor incorporated very wide-band phased array antennas in its nose and side windows. The ESM module, the passive surveillance coherent signal processor in the form of a Digital Signal Processor (DSP) was included in this testbed. The outputs from the DSP were inputs to a multi-target tracker, GPS/navigation computer, and target tracking display monitor where PPI tracks are displayed in real-time against a map background, as shown in Fig. 2. The successful operation of ESM illuminator finder, selection and pass off to the surveillance operation lies in the ability to discriminate useful ambient illuminators and target echoes from the radio frequency interference (RFI) background noise.

Finally, returning to Figs. 1A and 1B, and remembering that the sensor processes target echoes with the direct path reference signal, or collectively coherently, let us address now the potential of imaging targets. Regardless what the ambient noncooperative background signal is, its target echo will be coherent to the direct path signal. Thus, we can apply another processing mode in addition to the ESM and surveillance (target tracking) modes to exploit the coherent nature of these signals (echoes relative to the direct path). This third mode, afforded by the coherent nature of this sensor concept, is a tomographic imaging mode. In Fig. 1A, the target is a localized field of scatters (scattering points, or point images), were all scattering centers produce target

echoes which are coherent relative to the direct path, and discriminating via their distinct phase, time delays, Doppler shifts, and angle of arrival relationships as detected at the sensor receiver aperture. As the target traverses its target space, these localized scattering fields generate phasor records as a trace of the instantaneous scattering vector through time-space domains. Processing this vectorial trace as a target represented scattering record with time and geometric aspect produces a phasor phase relationship which is distinctly related to the target shape and motion-aspect history. This target historical pattern, when processed as a coherent-phase relationship, produces a phasor image of the target scattering field, similar to a hologram in the optical spectrum, but here as a phase, or tomographical image (phase-geometry-spatial relationships uniquely associated with the target scattering and motion characteristics).

A test was conducted to study the performance of target tomographic imaging based on ambient background signal exploitation. A trade-off exists between illuminator signal bandwidth versus the number of illuminators exploited for tomographical imaging. The results of this test are shown in Fig. 3 as a function of the number of illuminators exploited. The test target was a T-39 aircraft flying a nominal flight course in regions where many noncooperative illuminators were available (metropolitan regions where many broadcast stations are operating). Note, the overall silhouette of the T-39 can be distinctly discerned. It has fuel pods at the end of its non-swept wings, two engines located in its tail region, and the complex structure of the elevated vertical stabilizer and ruder assembly, all clearly visible in the multiple illuminator cased, less so as the number of illuminators decrease below 15 in number. The best silhouette image occurs when the most illuminators are available. This is due to the spatial diversity features of coherent tomographic imaging. That is, differing illuminators represent different geometrical aspects relative to the target and its own aspect to each illuminator. Multiple illuminators provide multiple aspects to the common target scattering structure (remembering a target is simply a scattering field with a certain aspect which is a function of geometry and time). As long as a direct path sample can be observed for each illuminator, the spatial phase coherency is maintained for each illuminator and each target point scatterer. The tomographic imaging process utilizes these phase relationships to process the target silhouette. The silhouette is highly lighted by distinct body glints (note these effects in Fig. 3). Another key factor in tomographically processing an image is the availability of a persistent scatterer throughout the image processing period. Such a scatterer can be found by examining the Doppler-Time-Intensity (DTI) data record. In this data record, a persistent scatterer can be found over a long time period (equivalent to an angular motion span exceeding 20 degrees horizontally). Such scatterers are automatically selected as a target localized phase reference by the tomographic imaging process. This allows the aspect of the target scattering field to be mapped in time and with target motion. Another factor can be derived from the DTI. That is, the predominant persistent scatterer can be used to remove the effective fringes which occur in coherent target imaging. This fringe cleaning process is done by a nestled processing routine in the tomographic imaging algorithm.

Figure 3. Passive Imaging, Simulation vs Test Data (T-39 Target)